

DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF BRAIN MENINGIOMAS

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Introduction. Meningiomas are tumors originating from the meninges of the brain. They are typically slow-growing and benign. These tumors are well-defined, round in shape, often calcified, and characterized by pronounced angiogenesis. Due to their expansive growth, they compress surrounding tissues without infiltrating them. Early diagnosis and the identification of optimal treatment strategies for meningiomas are of significant clinical importance.

Research objective. Assessment of Brain Meningiomas Based on Modern Diagnostic Techniques and Surgical Treatment Outcomes.

Materials and methods. A total of 55 patients with brain meningioma were included in the study. They underwent clinical and neurological assessments, CT/MRI for tumor evaluation, and angiography for blood supply analysis. Surgical treatments included embolization to reduce blood flow and intraoperative bleeding, and craniotomy for tumor removal. Postoperative outcomes were evaluated through neurological assessment, imaging (MRI/CT) for residual tumor detection, and the Karnofsky scale for functional status.

Research results. The study included 55 patients diagnosed with brain meningiomas. Among them, 65% were women, and 35% were men, with the highest incidence observed in the 40–60 age group (58%). The main symptoms were headache (82%), epileptic seizures (43%), visual impairment (37%), and cognitive dysfunction (29%). The chi-square test results indicated that epileptic seizures and headaches were significantly associated with tumor location ($P < 0.05$). All patients underwent CT (100%), MRI (58%), and angiography (33%). Angiography was primarily performed in patients scheduled for embolization. As a result, the embolized group experienced reduced blood loss and shorter surgery duration ($P < 0.01$). A total of 30 patients underwent embolization before surgery, while 25 patients underwent direct surgery. The operation duration in the embolized group was 3.5 ± 0.6 hours, whereas in the non-embolized group, it was 5.2 ± 0.8 hours ($P < 0.05$). Blood loss was 400 ± 150 ml in the embolized group and 800 ± 250 ml in the non-embolized group ($P < 0.01$). The need for blood transfusion was 5% in the embolized group compared to 36% in the non-embolized group ($P < 0.01$). Postoperative complications were observed in 10% of embolized patients and 32% of non-embolized patients ($P < 0.05$). The hospital stay was 6.2 ± 1.5 days in the embolized group and 9.8 ± 2.1 days in the non-embolized group ($P < 0.05$). Functional recovery was assessed using the Karnofsky Performance Scale. The preoperative score was 70 ± 10 , which improved to 85 ± 8 postoperatively ($P < 0.05$). The embolized group showed better recovery, with a postoperative score of 90 ± 6 ($P < 0.05$). Neurological complications were observed in 16% of patients, infectious complications in 8%, venous thrombosis in 6%, and epileptic syndrome in 5%. Complication rates were lower in the embolized group ($P < 0.05$). Surgical outcomes were evaluated using the Simpson classification. Total tumor resection (Simpson I–II) was achieved in 80% of cases, while subtotal resection (Simpson III–IV) was performed in 20% of cases. Brain meningiomas are most commonly observed in patients aged 40–60, with 65% of cases occurring in women. Embolization before surgery significantly reduced operation duration, blood loss, and the need for transfusion ($P < 0.01$). Postoperative functional recovery improved, particularly in the embolized group ($P < 0.05$). Higher surgical radicality (Simpson I–II) was associated with a lower recurrence

risk ($P < 0.05$).

Conclusions. Brain meningiomas are most commonly found in women aged 40–60 (65%). The main symptoms included headaches (82%), epileptic seizures (43%), visual impairments (37%), and cognitive dysfunction (29%). Preoperative embolization provided the following benefits: reduced operation time (3.5 hours vs. 5.2 hours, $P < 0.05$), decreased blood loss (400 ml vs. 800 ml, $P < 0.01$), lower need for blood transfusion (5% vs. 36%, $P < 0.01$), fewer complications (10% vs. 32%, $P < 0.05$), and faster recovery (6.2 days vs. 9.8 days, $P < 0.05$). According to the Simpson classification, total resection (Simpson I–II) was achieved in 80% of cases, reducing the likelihood of tumor recurrence. Surgery combined with embolization reduces operative risks and improves patient recovery. Further advancements in diagnostic and treatment methods remain essential for optimizing outcomes.